

THE WORD FORMATION CHARACTERISTICS OF ONLINE ENGLISH.

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Rakhimjonova Dilshoda Abubakir qizi

Fergana branch of Tashkent University of Information Technologies

Abstract: *With the development of Internet technology, people's lifestyle has undergone great changes, and it also affects people's language. As an international language, English has evolved and innovated on the Internet as a platform for people to communicate. A lot of new vocabulary has been born. As a new language, online English new vocabulary has been widely concerned and loved by people. Internet users can send e-mails on the Internet, e-shopping, e-commerce, etc., all of which require netizens to master certain new vocabulary of online English to be more convenient and effective. Based on the analysis of the reasons for the new vocabulary of online English, this paper analyzes the word formation characteristics and word formation rules of online English new vocabulary.*

Key words: *online English, compounding, acronyms, abbreviations, digital, Synthetic Lexical, prefixation, Derivative Lexical, word formation.*

The new vocabulary of online English is characterized by convenience, freedom, entertainment and fashion. First of all, in the fast-developing information age, people's life rhythm is accelerating. In order to facilitate the exchange of convenient language, the characteristics of network communication are concentrated and efficient. So replacing the lengthy and complicated sentences with a new and concise English vocabulary can save a lot of time and at the same time get the information you want. For example, you can use a homonym to borrow abbreviations, initial acronyms, shortened abbreviations and other abbreviations, or derivative words, synthetic words to express your emotional psychology, which also reduces the pressure to learn to master new words, can directly recombine from the original English vocabulary into new vocabulary to express different meanings, these new vocabulary plus the application of expression symbols can express the most effective and simple information in the shortest time. The application of the new vocabulary of online English reflects the ability to adapt to the modern fast-paced life, satisfying people's pursuit of high-efficiency psychological needs. When communicating on the Internet, these new words or emojis can be used to express information or emotions directly, saving money. The time of typing saves time on the Internet. The network can transform

some vocabulary to create a new English vocabulary, reflecting the simplicity and quickness of communication on the Internet. Secondly, the development of language must rely on social development. The same is true for online English. Once it is separated from the real society, it loses its foundation for survival and development. Language is also an important tool to reflect society. When there is a new phenomenon, it can have multiple forms of language expression. For example, e-commerce has two expressions: e-business and e-commerce. As a powerful language, English vocabulary continues to grow and develop with the continuous development of the network and the continuous expansion of the network scale. The vocabulary will continue to expand and update in daily life. In the age of information, people pursue freedom and individuality. Similarly, in the online society, the new generation is a generation of active thinking, individuality and freedom, so they are reluctant to use the long, complicated and modeled traditional English expressions. The creation of novel and unique network language on the Internet is an inevitable trend. It is an important way to reflect the relative freedom of the online virtual society, the individualized development of the young generation, and the full and free expression. Therefore, the new vocabulary of online English has the distinctive features of richness, freedom and interoperability, which can attract the attention of the young generation who pursue freedom. And these new and dynamic vocabulary have certain entertainment meanings in the network communication, people can achieve physical and mental pleasure when they use these new network words easily. In addition, the new online English vocabulary also has a certain sense of fashion. This is because the network English new word formation contains a large number of digital elements. In addition, as a new linguistic phenomenon, it also embodies the challenge of traditional English vocabulary. Because of its own personalization and fashion sense, it has attracted people's attention and jumped out from the traditional English vocabulary. The rapid spread and popularity of this new vocabulary with fashion has become one of the popular language forms.

A. Synthetic Lexical.

Synthetic method is a way of combining two or more words to form a new vocabulary. A synthetic word can be composed of two or more roots in appearance, but has only one word function in grammar and meaning. There are many synthetic words in the new vocabulary of online English. You could say it is completely out of control - that is the idea of the Internet: no censorship. Sometimes word formations look a little bit strange and it can be rather confusing.

Not only the establishment is empowered to create new words or word-formations. Even enterprises or private people are enabled to do so. There is only one determining rule: everything is possible.

The most common classifications seem to be:

- 1- compound nouns
- 2- compound verbs
- 3- compound adjectives
- 4- compound adverbs
- 5- and some others that are not always clear

These and all other classifications are combined by noun+verb, verb+noun, noun+adjective, adjective+noun, verb+adjective, adjective+verb, noun+particle ...and so on.

Some noun-noun compounds:

- *Address-Spoofing*: (to) log-in while using another Internet-Address
- *Bit rate*: (bps = Bits per second) figures for data transfer when uploading/downloading
- *Content pages*: pages of online presentations, normally navigations and advertisement pages
- *Country Code*: part of the Internet address or domain name, serves as criterion for the country e.g. ".de" of Germany
- *DocMaster*: editor who's generating and hosting the domain name
- *Domain Name*: part of the URL, after "http://" or "http://www." And finishes with the domain, e.g. ".de" or ".com" or ".edu").
- *Homepage*: main page of a website
- *Internet Nanny*: to protect children so that they are not able to reach pages with adult content; inter- is an prefix
- *Hard disk space*: space for saving information on the drives
- *Web- Appliances*: applications designed for the Internet, e.g. browser, download-proggy (but it seems as web is often used as prefix to, e.g. *web pad*)
- *Dreamcast and PlayStation*: both computers for gaming (also to play music and surfing the web) not for working; PlayStation is often used as synonym for gaming computers
- *Network Installation*: installation of a computer network
- *Express Installation*: fast set-up
- *Knowledgebase*: all known stuff about specific problems etc. on a homepage etc.
- *Personal Firewall*: hard- or software solution that helps to keep intranets/computers secure

B. Derivative Lexical

In the context of the Internet, new phenomena appearing for new things need to be explained by longer sentences. Based on this situation, there is also a derivative or composite way to create new vocabulary in online English, which is more convenient for new things. In the derivation of word formation, a new vocabulary is formed by adding a prefix or suffix on the basis of the original vocabulary. For example, the e- prefix often appears in the new vocabulary of online English. It has the meaning of network and electronic. It can be added in front of words such as book and life, which means e-books and online life. Inter-, net-, web-, re-, pre-, tele- and other prefixes are also often found in the new network English vocabulary, Inter means between each other, such as interactive (interactive), interface (interactive interface), Net is related to the network, such as net-worm (networm); re- means once again, such as reboot (reboot); pre indicates pre-, such as preview; tele- indicates Long distance, such as teleconferencing (teleconferencing), telemarketing (remote shopping); digit-representing digital networks, such as digitcam (digital camera), digeraid (network expert); -naut suffix often indicates the use of certain aspects Operators, such as internaut (online roamers), cybernaut (network users), etc.; micro-prefixes represent micro, network, such as micromoney (network micro-money), microserf (persons indulged in the network); -ware suffix indicates some kind of software, such as freeware (freeware), shareware (shareware).

Words with prefixes are out of control as well. Sometimes there exist two or three or more prefixes for the same idea. The overlapping meaning of some prefixes causes this fact. Really good examples here are *e-/tele-/cyber-/inter-* or *online - shop*, which have all nearly, complete the same meaning - the same facility: a shop where you can buy an article (similar to mail order services) via its homepage. Caused by the inflationary utilization only some of the most important prefixes are shown below.

- *e-*: stands for electronic: e-commerce, e-business, eBay (name of an Internet-company), e-volution...

- *tele-*: is the prefix for far away, over a longer distance etc.: television, teletutoring, teleuniversity, teletubbies...

- *cyber-*: stands for 3D virtuality, the internet etc.: cybergeography/cybermapping (pictures...); cybergeography: Multi User Dimensions (MUDs)/Virtual Worlds: very famous Ultima Online etc. graphical 3D virtual worlds, Cyberspace, 3D electronic space, virtual worlds Abandon all hope (MUD) HyperSpace

- *inter-*, *intra-*: both imply the meaning of connecting between something/somebody, especially via the new medias: intranet as the network within one corporation/enterprise etc. (if you want the very own internet only for “a special membership”) ; Internet as the whole network expanding all over the world

D. Acronyms and abbreviations.

When people communicate on the Internet, in order to pursue convenience and efficiency, to get the most information they need in the shortest time, or to express what they want, they need to use concise words, and related acronyms are produced. There are mainly the following types of abbreviated word formation: the first homonym borrowing abbreviations: such as IC (I see), Y (why), U (you) and so on. Initial acronyms: such as IOW (in other words), LOL (laughing out loud), BF (boyfriend), BTW (by the way) TY (thank you), BBL (be back later), YHL (you have lost) and many more. Truncated abbreviations: such as hang on a sec (hang on a second), rep (reputation), PLS (please), PS (postscript), THX (thanks), PPL (people) and so on.

For a better understanding of the very common use of acronyms I will first give some definitions. Acronyms can be built by derivation and compounding. Even the term ACRONYM is an acronym, too. The very popular website V.E.R.A. (Virtual Entity of Relevant Acronyms) for instance is an acronym (although here of course the name is program). Sometimes one can notice acronyms (or abbreviations) written with periods after each letter (e.g., *U.S.A.*).

The Worldwide Web Acronym and Abbreviation Server gives us some definitions: ...an acronym is any string of characters formed from the initial letters of several words (or occasionally from other letters), regardless of whether the result is pronounceable or not. Here is an example of an acronym: North Atlantic Treaty Organization = NATO. An acronym is a pronounceable word formed from each of the first letters of a descriptive phrase. An acronym is actually a type of abbreviation. There are of course some differences between one group, which is spoken as a word and one that is spoken as initials. And here some very common examples of the first group found on the Internet:

- *LAN*: the Local Area Network is commonly a “smaller area” network; e.g. so called LAN-Parties which take place in a semi-detached house or often as event or competition in a former factory hall etc.

- *WAN*: the Wider Area Network is the bigger counter part (if you want the Internet for the intranets)

- *WAP*: Wireless Application Protocol

- *ICANN*: Internet Corporation for Assigned Names and Numbers (directory of the Internet administration)

- *HTTP* etc.: the typical used transfer protocol which is necessary to read/send information, the Hypertext Transfer Protocol is in use on Internet for the PCs, same goes for the *WAP* which does the same for handy to send/receive web informations

Borrowing digital thumbnails is also an interesting alternative: for example, o2o (online to online), F2F (face to face) 2b or not 2b (to be or not to be), 4GET (forget), and so on. It should be noted that borrowing digital abbreviations is based on digital and language-like pronunciations. For example, the 2 and to pronunciations are similar, and the 4 and for pronunciations are similar. The expression of homonymous and homophonic digital word formation is combined with the pronunciation of English words, and the meaning to be expressed is expressed in a more convenient and concise way. Other really nice examples are *Y2K and W3*. *Y2K* contains not only the initials of some words. The initial Y stands for year, the number 2 for itself and K for kilo in its prefixation-meaning for thousand. If you read this in context the result is Year two thousand. This acronym was often used in connection with the upcoming new millennium in the last years of the 90's in 20th century and especially common a word formation *Y2K Bug* caused by the feared trouble for the *EDP* (Electronic Data Processing). *W3* is only one of several nicknames for the World Wide Web. The most URLs contain *www* as first part of their address.

Then we have also a group of acronyms called homonymous which are spoken as a still existing word but in a second meaning:

- *BASIC*: Beginners All-purpose Symbolic Instruction Code, a programming language that survived as MS Visual Basic.

- *FAQ*: to pronounce as the typical slang word fuck, but nevertheless with a more positive meaning Frequently Asked Questions (often as section on a homepage similar to a forum for troubleshooting etc.)

- *EDGE*: Enhanced Data Rates for GSM Evolution is the last step on the GSM based networks but under the viewpoint of reaching the UMTS

Especially digeratis are very innovative in acronym-speak. Acronyms are not only used as words. The popular sport *Gotcha* for instance stays for a whole sentence that says: I got ya! Another acronym-speak is *ICQ* for "I Seek You"- it is one of the most popular Web utilities around. What makes this instant chat tool a favorite among Netizens is its ability to locate friends and colleagues online and alert you when they are available to chat. Unlike some other chat tools, which seem

to cater to teenagers, this one is gaining popularity among business users as a handy communication tool, and it is free of charge.

In summary, with the continuous development of computer network technology and the deepening of informatization and network globalization, in this virtualized and open cyberspace world, the language required for communication is constantly changing. Combine with the characteristics of the times to pursue more diverse, free, concise, individual and efficient expression. The emergence of new vocabulary in online English enables people to express information and emotions more conveniently and vividly in online communication, and is more easily accepted by people. The development and application of new vocabulary in online English is efficient and fast-paced in modern society.

REFERENCES:

1. Cherny, Lynn. 1999. *Conversation and community: chat in a virtual world*. Stanford, CA: CSLI Publications
2. Dorner, Jane. 1992. Virtual English. *English Today* 32, 29-34.
2000. *The Internet: a writer's guide*. London: A. and C. Black.
3. Xie Yi. Analysis of the characteristics of word formation in online English. *Modern Communication*, 2017 (24): 96-96.
4. Hu Yuxuan. On the characteristics of online English vocabulary. *Neijiang Science and Technology*, 2018 (05): 106+114.
5. Tan Jing. Analysis of the characteristics and forms of word formation in current network English. *Southern Vocational Education Journal*, 2016(04):80-84.